

OVERVIEW OF SINGLE DEGREE OF FREEDOM EXPERIMENTS OF VERTICAL SLOSHING FLOWS INSIDE SCALED TANKS

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Abstract: This work presents the outcomes of several research groups after three years of experimental activities, part of the EU Horizon 2020 SLOWD project, related with the study of violent sloshing in an aeronautical context. The paper describes the different experimental rigs that the project partners have designed in order to measure the effects of liquid sloshing on vertically vibrating tanks. A wide variety of experiments have been performed either using periodic forced actuation or transient decaying motion. The most important results observed in the experiments in terms of tank acceleration, fluid added damping, sloshing forces and dissipated energy as functions of fill-level, excitation level and normalised excitation frequency are shown. The overlapping conclusions from both sets of quantitative and qualitative results, as well as their physical interpretation, show a remarkable consistency despite the independent nature of the experimental rig designs.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aircraft wings are highly flexible structures, which deform significantly when atmospheric turbulence or gusts is encountered, where the deformations can reach 20% of the wing span in the most severe cases. The wings also house the fuel tanks, generally carrying an amount of fuel comparable in weight to that of their structural components. Standard engineering practices for wing (and entire aircraft) design do not consider the effect of the fuel movement within the tanks for the determination of the aircraft design loads. The typical aircraft development cycle includes two major experimental tests (Ground Vibration and Flight Flutter) to identify/verify the dynamic characteristics of the aircraft structure. However, these tests are limited to small amplitudes and therefore are unlikely to excite significant sloshing modes.

In this context, the research performed during the EU funded SLOWD project aims to quantify the extent to which liquid sloshing in the aircraft tanks affects the structural damping, and thus the structural dynamic and aeroelastic behaviour of an airliner. One of the main objectives of the SLOWD project is to present a set of experimental campaigns ranging from single degree of freedom scaled experiments, and then adding complexity up to a full-scale wing experiment including fuel tanks. This structure will be excited at a range of amplitudes where sloshing effects are likely to occur. Preliminary transient experimental studies were carried out on a sloshing beam [1] which indicated that the amount of damping due to the sloshing motion depended upon the fill level in the tanks. Although a good example of the possibility of exploiting fuel sloshing motion to impart added damping to aircraft wing motion, it was a difficult set-up for comparing the various fluid sloshing modelling capabilities being developed in the SLOWD project.

Consequently, in order to reduce the complexity of analysis and to isolate the vertical component of the sloshing motion, several simpler experiments were designed by three members of the SLOWD consortium. These experimental tests aimed to satisfy two main objectives: first, to create a complete database to test the numerical models

Figure 1: UB T-beam experimental schematic and setup outline. (1) Stainless steel beams, (2) Acrylic tank containing tap water, (3) Added mass, (4) Accelerometer, (5) Loading mechanism (turnbuckle), (6) High speed camera.

also developed in the project, and secondly to understand the complexity of liquid sloshing in this context where turbulence and violent impacts have a dominant role.

In this work, a review of the experiments based on the single degree of freedom test rigs carried out in the SLOWD project is presented. The presentation and analysis of the experimental data is based on the type of excitation that was used and is thus split in two parts: transient (step release) and harmonic tests. The experimental rigs and test methodology are presented in Section 2 and the main results and outcomes are discussed in Section 3.

2 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACHES

2.1 Single Degree of Freedom Transient Tests

The first type of experiments performed investigated the decaying transient behaviour, where an elastic beam is deformed and released and the evolution of the system oscillations is studied. Conceptually, a single degree of freedom vertically-vibrating system is needed for this type of investigations, as shown in Figure 1(a): a partially-filled liquid tank placed on a linearly elastic (k), lightly damped (small c), grounded element. The main requirements for such a system are: exclusively vertical motion, large-amplitudes of vibrations in the linear stiffness domain and low structural damping. These requirements are necessary for the isolation of the sloshing-induced effects under vertical transient motion.

The first approach to this problem was formulated by the University of Bristol (UB), see Figure 1, where a flexure-type configuration was manufactured which consisted of two perpendicular steel strips, (1) in Figure 1(b), forming a "T-beam" configuration with its three ends constrained. A tank (2) (height $h = 20$ mm, length $L = 60$ mm and width $w = 30$ mm) was placed in the middle of the horizontal beam alongside an additional mass (3) to maintain dynamic equivalence between tests at various filling levels. The system was loaded vertically using a turnbuckle (5) and released by cutting the wire, and the response of the system was measured using an accelerometer (4) placed under the tank. This experimental arrangement showed only one dominant lightly damped vibration mode with a linear domain extending up to at least 14 strip thicknesses. These properties made the chosen configuration ideal for vertical transient sloshing studies. The amplitudes of excitation studied here are in the range of 1 – 14mm and filling levels between 0 and 100% with increments of 10% are considered as well. A detailed description and analysis of this experiment can be found in [2].

A second SDOF sloshing experimental campaign was conducted at the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (UPM) in order to investigate the slosh-induced damping effects in Froude scaled tanks subjected to vertical accelerations. A photograph of the 1/5 scale experimental setup at the Model Basin Research group sloshing laboratory of the UPM is shown in the top part of Figure 2. The sloshing rig is a 1 degree of freedom system including a mechanical guide that only allows vertical motion. This guide is attached to C-shaped wooden structure that holds the tank

Figure 2: Top: Experimental UPM setup. (1) Load cell, (2) Metallic plate, (3) Upper set of springs, (4) Lower set of springs, (5) Laser sensor, (6) Mechanical guide, (7) Accelerometer, (8) Methacrylate tank and C-shaped wooden structure, (9) Pair of solenoids acting as release mechanism. Bottom: Tested tanks for 1/6 , 1/5 and 1/4 scales along with their dimensions and characteristic frequencies.

which is also attached to a set of 6 springs (3 on the upper side and 3 on the lower side) each of them having an individual spring constant of $k_i = 708.3$ N/m. The lower springs are mechanically embedded to the floor and on the opposite side. The upper set of springs is attached to a metallic plate that acts as a joint between the springs and the embedded load cell.

The structure is deflected a certain displacement y_0 until it is fixed by the action of both solenoids. These permanent solenoids are able to produce a magnetic force of 400 N, allowing the system to remain fixed at vertical deflection $y = y_0$. When the electrical current is turned on they release the structure, triggering the oscillatory transient movement. The solid moving mass m_s accounts for the masses of the C-shaped wooden structure, tank, mechanical bearing system and attachments, and m_l represents the liquid mass inside of the tank. The total mass of the system $m = m_l + m_s$ is constant for each scaling assuring that the natural frequency of the system follows the Froude scaling laws. More details can be found in [3].

In this second experimental setup there are 3 magnitudes that were measured: the acceleration, the position of the tank and the force at point (1) in Figure 2. The acceleration of the moving solid mass is measured by a piezo-electric accelerometer, the position is measured by a single point laser sensor and the force is measured by a S-type load cell. The measured signals of this experiment are presented in section 3 after filtering with a 4th order Butterworth filter and a cutoff frequency of 20 Hz. Once the acceleration, position and force measurements are post-processed, the damping ratio and vertical sloshing force are derived.

The experimental campaign carried out by UPM consisted in analyzing three different tank scales 1:6, 1:5 and 1:4, see bottom Figure 2. For each scale different filling levels, different fluids (kerosene, glycerine, Diesel B, oil, water and Tetrachloroethylene) either tested at constant filling level or at constant mass ratio and being also the initial deformations y_0 another parameter of the experiment. A number of repetitions of the tests have been done for certain cases to measure the experimental errors of the campaign.

2.2 Single Degree of Freedom Harmonic Tests

The second type of experiments that were designed employed a linear actuator to impose a controlled vertical sinusoidal motion on the sloshing system. Compared to the transient cases described above, where free vertical vibrations following a step-release were used, there are several advantages of using a linear actuator to study

sloshing-induced damping, the most important being:

- The ability to focus and isolate a single sloshing mode in a controllable manner,
- The ability to study a sloshing mode of interest under periodically steady-state conditions characterised by the harmonic inputs within certain range of the input frequencies and amplitudes,
- The minimisation of the various parasitic effects such as dry friction and spatial motion irregularity.

Figure 3: Upper left: UB electroactuator experimental rig. Upper right: UB long-stroke electrodynamic shaker. Lower: electrodynamic shaker and parallel-piped Plexiglass tank used by Sapienza University of Rome

The first experimental harmonic campaign, presented in [4], took place in the structural dynamics laboratory of La Sapienza University in Rome (USRS) and it was conducted to investigate the dissipative behaviour of the fluid sloshing inside a tank set in vertical motion. A controlled electrodynamic shaker is employed to provide vertical displacement by means of sine-sweep excitation: the considered frequency and amplitude ranges are such to characterise the dissipation introduced by the fluid in conditions of small perturbations (low values of g) as well as at high accelerations. Under these conditions where the imposed acceleration is high, dissipative phenomena become the most intense as the free surface of the fluid breaks up and impact mechanisms with the tank walls arise. The experiment in hand is shown in the lower section of Figure 3. It consists of a box-shaped tank made in Plexiglass with a height of $h = 27.2$ mm and base of sides $l_1 = 117.2$ mm and $l_2 = 78.0$ mm. The dimensions are chosen

Figure 4: Frequency-amplitude pairs spanned during different sine sweep tests conducted by Sapienza University of Rome

in order to trigger slamming with the tank roof following Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities. The test design provides that three different filling levels featured by $\alpha = h_f/h$ (with h_f the liquid depth) are taken into consideration, *i.e.*, $\alpha = 0.50$ (case 1, reference), $\alpha = 0.25$ (case 2) and $\alpha = 0.75$ (case 3). The liquid tested in each of the cases listed is water. The tank is placed over a controlled electrodynamic shaker able to impose vertical sinusoidal displacements from a lower frequency of 5 Hz, and able to reach a 25 mm peak-to-peak displacement amplitude. The dynamic load at the interface between shaker and tank is measured by two load cells, placed in the middle of the long side of the tank base. The overall force exchanged by tank and shaker is the sum of the two load cells. The system is also equipped with two redundant accelerometers placed at the opposite corners of the tank upper closing side and with a control accelerometer used by the shaker sine-sweep controller.

The black curves showed in Figure 4(a) illustrate the chosen paths for the sine-sweep tests. The O indicate the starting points (at 5 Hz) while the F indicate the ending points (at 20 Hz). Except for the first three branches, the other branches start from O_4 thus reaching the final points F_5 , F_6 and so on, but initially following the dashed line indicating a displacement of about 12.5 mm due to the aforementioned shaker limits. Figure 4(b) shows the same result but using the displacement amplitude instead of the acceleration. The minimum (0.25 g) and maximum (6 g) iso-acceleration curves therefore define the domain where the energy dissipated by the fluid inside the tank is identified experimentally. The instantaneous frequency of tests performed varies very slowly and consequently, around a generic time instant, the frequency is almost constant, at least for a limited number of cycles. The work exchanged between the fluid and the shaker defines the dissipation that we want to characterise and it is calculated by averaging over a number of cycles where the frequency can be assumed to be constant. For a generic time instant indicated as t_k , the energy dissipated W is calculated as

$$W(\Omega(t_k), a_0(t_k)) = \frac{1}{N_c} \int F_S(\Omega(\tau), a_0(\tau)) \dot{u}(\tau) d\tau \quad (1)$$

where N_c represents the number of cycles over which the averaging operation is performed. Index k corresponds to the time instant in which the work calculation is performed and is carefully selected to avoid overlapping with the cycles considered for the averaging (the number of which is precisely N_c). F_S is the sloshing force measured by means of the load cells and depends on both the frequency Ω and the amplitude a_0 of the acceleration of the motion imposed by the shaker (whose velocity is indicated as \dot{u}). More details can be found in Ref. [4]. The results of the present activity can be also reported in a non-dimensional form. We consider the non-dimensional versions of the operating parameters, thus the frequency Ω and amplitude of the vertical displacement u_0 , defined respectively as $\bar{\omega} = \Omega/\sqrt{g/h}$ and $\bar{u} = u_0/h$. The non-dimensional work exchanged between the tank and the shaker is defined as $\bar{W} = W/(m_l u_0^2 \Omega^2)$, where m_l is the liquid mass. These non-dimensional results take into consideration only the operational parameters without considering the dependency of the phenomenon to parameters addressing the physics and tank size, such as free surface effects and the viscosity. Note that if one were to integrate the tank under consideration into a structural system, the above non-dimensional energy would relate directly to the concept of loss factor. Reference [5] provided a definition of loss factor by means of the ratio between the dissipated energy and a reference kinetic energy stored by the containing structure. The work mentioned, not included in this article for the sake of conciseness, was also carried out as part of the European project, in the laboratories of La Sapienza University in Rome. In it, an investigation was carried out into the damping mechanisms induced by sloshing in a system consisting of a cantilever beam which had a tank partially filled with water positioned at its tip. The dissipative behaviour of the system was studied by varying the frequency and amplitude of the random excitation that was imposed at the beam joint.

The approach taken at the University of Bristol focused on two large-amplitude vertical actuators shown in the upper section of Figure 3 [6]. The experimental setups consisted of a vertical actuator capable of large amplitudes of

Figure 5: Harmonic excitation tests matrix conducted at the University of Bristol

Figure 6: Amplitude – frequency map of the different experimental facilities for the study of vertical sloshing

motion (either electromechanical actuator or long-stroke electrodynamic shaker) grounded on a vibration isolation table. The two actuators were used in order to expand the test matrix, as the electromechanical actuator was found to be limited in the achievable accelerations and also presented more mechanical noise. Two tanks partially filled with liquid (tank 1: $h = 37.5\text{mm}$, $L = 100\text{mm}$, $w = 30\text{mm}$; tank 2: $h = 50\text{mm}$, $L = 100\text{mm}$, $w = 30\text{mm}$) were placed at the end of the actuator with an accelerometer and force sensor in between. Two tanks were used in order to investigate the influence of tank height and selected results for $h = 37.5\text{mm}$ are presented and discussed here. The tests were conducted according to the test matrix in Figures 5 and 6, spanning a large amplitude and frequency range. Considering that the tests were conducted separately at set amplitude and frequency, the tank acceleration information obtained from one single accelerometer was sufficient to completely describe, using suitable processing of the data, the displacement, velocity and acceleration of the tank. The force sensor placed between the actuator and the tank was used to isolate the force due to the moving liquid exclusively, according to [6] such that

$$F_s = F - (m_w + m_s)a \quad (2)$$

where F_s is the force due to sloshing liquid, F is the total force obtained from the force sensor at the tank-actuator interface, m_w and m_s are the mass of water and dry components placed on top of the sensor respectively, and a is the tank acceleration signal, obtained from the accelerometer. This force was then integrated with respect to tank displacement and normalized to obtain the non-dimensional energy dissipation measure [6]

(a) Acceleration signal time series
 (b) Envelope of the acceleration signal
 Figure 7: UB Transient acceleration mean value (black) and confidence bounds (red) for 50 % fill level

$$E_c = \frac{1}{m_w \omega^2 A^2} \frac{1}{N_c} \int F_s dz \quad (3)$$

where E_c is the non-dimensional dissipative energy per tank cycle due to sloshing, ω and A are the frequency and amplitude of excitation, N_c is the number of cycles averaged over and z is the instantaneous tank vertical displacement.

The non-dimensional parameter range spanned by the transient and harmonic excitation tests presented here are synthesized in Figure 6. The amplitude-frequency of excitation range cover regions where all vertical sloshing regimes of typical aircraft wing structures are achieved. The transient and harmonic excitation experimental rigs presented here thus enable thorough investigations of vertical sloshing-induced damping across a wide range of excitation amplitudes and frequencies. In what follows, the main results that have been obtained based on the presented experiments are synthesized.

3 RESULTS

Some of the most relevant results obtained during the 1DOF experimental campaigns of the SLOWD consortium partners are discussed. The presentation of results is split into two parts: first, the results concerning the transient tests conducted at UB and UPM are presented; and then the harmonic excitation results based on the experimental campaigns at USRS and UB offer a complementary view on the vertical sloshing induced damping effects in single degree of freedom systems.

3.1 Transient Tests

Transient tests were conducted at the University of Bristol with multiple excitation amplitudes and filling levels. Figure 7 shows a typical sloshing tank acceleration response in time domain, with black curves indicating mean decaying acceleration data at each time and red bands showing minimum/ maximum confidence bounds among three similar tests. The cases shown here are for a 50% filling level. Figure 7(a) contains insets showing the single frequency dominance in the system, as well as the measured variability in the data and how it changes in time. Very good repeatability was observed. Figure 7(b) shows the envelopes of the same acceleration signals on a semi-logarithmic scale, with the damping ratio ζ computed using the slope of the envelope and expressed as percentage of the critical damping. The trends corresponding to the dry structure damping are shown as well in order to emphasize the marked difference introduced by liquid sloshing. One striking fact noticeable in Figure 7(b) is the piece-wise character of the envelope on the semi-logarithmic scale, indicative of separated damping trends. We call these observed regions R1-R3 and representative video captures from each region are shown in Figure 8. Qualitatively distinct liquid sloshing patterns are thus seen to correspond to quantitatively distinct damping ratios, as follows: R1 – the most dissipative region, dominated by violent vertical liquid impacts with the top and bottom

Figure 8: UB Typical liquid responses in each sloshing regime. R1 - violent vertical liquid impacts, R2 - sloshing mode-dominated patterns, R3 - low amplitude surface ripples.

of the tank; R2 – substantial energy dissipation caused by lower amplitude sloshing motions dominated by one or multiple liquid sloshing modes (mode (2,0) in the case shown in Figure 8) also known as Faraday waves; R3 – low amplitude surface ripples or no liquid movement at all, where the energy dissipation is the same as the low-amplitude dry structure.

The behaviour of the single degree of freedom transient systems were found to be highly dependent on amplitude of excitation and filling level. Figure 9 shows an example of such dependency, namely the evolution of the transient damping trends in time for different initial amplitudes a_0/g and filling level of 70%, starting with the lowest on the top. This map represents a collection of envelopes such as the ones shown in Figure 7(b), one per each horizontal dashed line and a_0/g values. The abscissa represents the time coordinate and $t = 0$ represents the step release event. This map shows regions where the damping ratio for the 70% filling level case is found between certain threshold values, characteristic of the three different liquid sloshing patterns R1-R3. While setting such threshold values is ultimately arbitrary, consistent dissipation trends are observed across all tests shown within the bounds of the regions in Figure 9, as the three regions are also seen to correspond to different tank vertical acceleration bounds. Importantly for this case, even at amplitudes of excitation such as 2.7g and lower, substantial energy dissipation occurs due to R2-sloshing behaviour.

Damping ratios were measured for these tests by a procedure consisting in fitting linear trends over the logarithm of the decaying acceleration envelopes. Since the trends were found to be piece-wise linear, the division between the three regions R1-R3 is not only supported by the observed qualitative sloshing pattern trends, but also by the quantitative data, each of the linear damping trends corresponding to each of the identified regions in Figure 9.

Sloshing-induced damping was also found to be heavily dependent on liquid filling level as well. Tests were conducted at UB for filling level starting from 0 to 100%, with increments of 10%, and a summary of all identified damping trends for the maximum excitation amplitude are shown in Figure 10. Both 0% and 100% show zero sloshing-induced dissipation, as there is no liquid or it does not move. Between the two extremes, the R1 damping ratio was found to increase until 50% filling level and then do decrease back. There is substantial symmetry about the 50% filling level. The R2 damping ratio was found to be less dependent on filling level, since damping in this region is dominated by certain liquid sloshing patterns in which filling level plays only a limited role (frequency of excitation is the most important parameter here). Understanding the variation of damping to due vertical sloshing with respect to filling ratio is of utmost importance in exploiting the liquid sloshing action in order to maximize the induced damping effects.

Finally, a global view of the R1 sloshing-induced dissipation trends can be seen in Figure 11 for three filling levels and initial excitation amplitudes up to 7.5g. Each marker is one experimental data point corresponding to ζ_1 in the R1 region, and two straight lines were fitted in order to show the damping trends. The damping ratio is seen to increase in value up to between 3 and 4g, after which it seems to reach a plateau with a slightly increasing trend. Larger amplitudes were not achievable in this setup, such that the large amplitude trends could not be established here. The R1 energy dissipation shows consistent variation with amplitude of excitation regardless of filling level with the damping saturation point found in the same region.

Using the UPM experimental rig described in section 2.1 and shown in Figure 2, several scales and configurations were tested. The first part of the campaign was based on the intermediate scale 1/5, where the main hypothesis

Figure 9: UB Damping ratio map $\zeta(a_0, t)$ for the 70% filling level case, showing the occurrence in time of the three different sloshing regimes

Figure 10: UB Variation of sloshing-induced damping with filling level for the three damping regions

of the project was verified that states that when a fraction of the structural mass is replaced by a liquid mass that is allowed to slosh the damping ratio of the whole system increases. In order to verify this thinking, two types of experiments are devised: dry and wet tests. In the dry tests there is no liquid mass in the system, allowing the computation of the structural damping ζ_d . From the damping ratio obtained from the wet tests ζ , we can derive the slosh-induced damping ratio $\Delta\zeta$ by subtracting the dry damping ratio from the wet one such that

$$\zeta = \zeta_d + \Delta\zeta \quad (4)$$

The time evolution of the accelerations of the tank and the envelope of the signals for the three selected scales are compared in Figure 12 for both the wet and dry mass tests. The frequency of the acceleration signals follows the Froude scaling laws and it scales as $\sqrt{\lambda}$, with λ being the scaling factor. It should be emphasised that the experiments confirm that a constant frequency was presented for the whole duration of the experimental test.

After some dimensional analysis of the problem, it is concluded, see [7], that the damping added by the liquid slosh $\Delta\zeta$ in our experiments depends on four non-dimensional numbers: the liquid density $\bar{\rho} = \rho/\rho_a$, filling level f , initial non-dimensional displacement of the tank y_0/h and mass ratio $r = m_l/m_s$. This relationship can be expressed mathematically as

$$\Delta\zeta = \mathcal{F}(\bar{\rho}, f, \frac{y_0}{h}, r) \quad (5)$$

which is valid for the decay experiments presented in this work. If an actuator were to be used to impose the motion of the tank, such as in the harmonic experiments described in section 2.2, the mass ratio r would lose its meaning

Figure 11: UB R1 damping ratio versus maximum acceleration

Figure 12: Left: Acceleration signal of the tank for wet and dry mass experiments performed at the UPM for the three selected scales. Right: Semi-logarithmic plot of the envelope of the acceleration signal for wet and dry mass experiments. The wet tests correspond to a 10g and 50% filling level water experiments.

and an additional non-dimensional number representing the natural frequency of the imposed motion would have to be added.

The damping ratios ζ and ζ_d are calculated by applying the Hilbert transform to the envelope signal from the acceleration peaks. The liquid induced damping ratio $\Delta\zeta$ is normalized with the reference case, which determines the reference damping variation value $\Delta\zeta_0$ that is computed when the liquid is water, the filling level is $f = 0.5$ and the initial deformation $y_0/h = 1$ which gives a maximum acceleration of $a_0 = 10g$. The evolution of the acceleration signal in time and the envelope of the acceleration signal with the explicit damping ratios ζ and ζ_d are represented for the reference case for scales 1/6, 1/5 and 1/4 in Figure 12. The explanation why the liquid induced damping ratio does not remain the same is that the mass ratio r is not conserved between scales.

In this experiment, a single linear trend is observed for the wet mass test as displayed in Figure 12. The mechanical guide adds extra dry friction damping to the system, mitigating the low amplitudes of the signal faster. Other less damped sloshing experiments such as the beam-tank test described in 2.1, reported in [1], and the UB tests described above [2] show a piece wise linear trend with three well distinguished regimes is observed for the acceleration envelopes, see Figure 8.

The sloshing force has been obtained via two different methods, either via a purely experimental approach or by following a semi-empirical method based on an analytical damping model, see further details in [3]. We can observe in Figure 13 that both approaches compute sloshing forces which are close to each other. In the same figure, a linear approximation to the vertical sloshing force is added as $F_{slosh} = m_l a + B_{1slosh} v$. Where, a and v are the acceleration and velocity of the tank respectively and $B_{1slosh} = B_1 - B_{1d}$ is the slosh-induced damping coefficient (in kg/s) obtained from the subtraction of the damping coefficients of the wet and dry tests.

Similarly to what was found for the tank acceleration, the sloshing force does not follow a perfect matching when scaled to the full size, and again it is observed that the mass ratio has an influence on the scaling. The vertical sloshing force in Figure 14, is presented for the three scales. Both time and force have been scaled up to the wing

Figure 13: Comparison between "Experimental" and "Semi-empirical" procedures for sloshing force calculation in a 50%, 10g and water test of scale 1/5. The blue line represents a linear approximation of the vertical sloshing force.

Figure 14: Vertical sloshing force for water tests at $f = 0.5$ and $y_0/H = 1$ for scales $\lambda = 1/6, 1/5, 1/4$.

size following the Froude scaling laws.

A number of water experiments varying inertial Froude number are performed with constant filling level $f = 0.5$, constant mass ratio $r = m_l/m_s$ and constant density ratio for each scale. This inertial Froude number is calculated as the non-dimensional initial amplitude $1/Fr = \sqrt{y_0/h}$ along the interval $y_0/h \in [0.1, 1]$. In Figure 15, the normalized slosh induced damping ratio is displayed as a function of the non-dimensional initial amplitude for all scales. Two distinguishable trends are observed, first, an increasing trend of the damping ratio is seen for low amplitudes up until a saturation point, then the system no longer provides an additional damping and it decreases for higher amplitudes. The observed saturation amplitude is at $y_0/h \approx 0.4$ for the three scales. Similar observations were made in the SDOF vertical sloshing experiments conducted in [2] for three different filling levels.

Figure 16 shows the evolution of the slosh-induced damping ratio as a function of the density ratio $\bar{\rho}$ for the three selected scales. This study was performed at constant filling level $f = 0.5$ and constant initial amplitude $y_0/h = 1$. The liquid inside of the tank was varied covering a range of liquid densities of $\rho \in [792.5, 1621] \text{ kg/m}^3$. As the liquid density increases, the related vertical sloshing forces are greater, resulting in higher liquid induced power dissipation. A similar trend was observed in [7] for the density ratio variation study at constant mass ratio.

Finally, the tank filling level f is varied in the interval $[0.1, 0.9]$ while keeping the density ratio $\bar{\rho}$ and initial displacement y_0/h constant. This approach results in a variation of the mass ratio r corresponding to changes in the filling level. The normalized slosh induced damping ratio $\Delta\zeta/\Delta\zeta_0$ with the reference case is presented as a function of the filling level in Figure 17 for the three selected scales. A maximum damping is observed for $f = 0.5$

Figure 15: Normalized slosh induced damping ratio as a function of the nondimensional initial amplitude for scales $\lambda = 1/6, 1/5, 1/4$.

Figure 16: Normalized slosh induced damping ratio as a function of the density ratio for scales $\lambda = 1/6, 1/5, 1/4$.

Figure 17: Normalized slosh induced damping as a function of the filling level for scales $\lambda = 1/6, 1/5, 1/4$.

which then decreases for higher and lower fill levels, whilst the minimum damping is observed for the highest and lowest fill levels $f = 0.1$ and $f = 0.9$. These results are consistent across the three scales. A similar tendency was observed in the decay experiments conducted in [2] where the filling level study was done for SDOF rig described in section 2.1. The symmetric shape shown in Figure 17 can be explained in terms of the two opposing trends of the sloshing force and the phase-shift, see [7].

3.2 Harmonic Tests

From the implementation of the tests shown in Figure 4 it has been possible to obtain very interesting results both in qualitative and quantitative terms, regarding the characterisation of the energy dissipated by vertical sloshing as the operating parameters vary for different filling levels. For the sake of conciseness the qualitative characterisation of the different fluid-dynamics regimes will be provided only for the reference filling level case $\alpha = 0.50$. Figure 18 shows 9 snapshots of the sloshing behaviour at different values of acceleration a_0 and frequency $f = 2\pi\Omega$, containing also the 6 red dots highlighted in Figure 4(b). Figures 18(a) to 18(c) refer to the test where Rayleigh-Taylor instability is not triggered and, therefore, the liquid does not experience any free surface breakage. Instead we see Faraday waves that are generated inside the tank, that may softly impact the tank ceiling (see Figures 18(a) and 18(b)). By increasing the frequency, the surface tension stabilises the free surface and impacts no longer occur (see Figure 18(c)). Next, when the acceleration values are greater than $1g$, we notice the transition to a more chaotic regime of the fluid, where the free surface breaks. This effect is noticeable in Figures 18(d) to 18(f), which are related to an acceleration level of $1.5g$ and it is no longer possible to identify coherent structures of the fluid. By increasing the frequency, more precisely at 13 Hz, a transition to a new standing waves regime is noticed with impacts occurring with less intensity (see Figure 18(e)). Figure 18(f) shows that above a certain frequency value there is no longer any presence of impacts. Finally, when the tank is set in motion at high acceleration values (*i.e.* with an acceleration of $3g$, see Figures 18(g) to 18(i)), the fluid inside the tank behaves chaotically for the whole considered range of frequencies. As for the characterisation of the dissipated energy, the filling level reference case $\alpha = 0.50$ is the first one considered in the analysis. Figure 19(a) shows the trend over time of the sloshing force while Figure 19(b) shows the hysteresis cycles obtained by plotting the variation of the same sloshing force with respect to the harmonic displacement of the tank (the curves shown are relative to point 6 only). The area enclosed by the cycles represents the dissipated work at the specific acceleration-frequency pair, as defined in Eq. 1. By extending this process of evaluating the dissipated energy to all the frequency and amplitude pairs spanned during the experimental tests, an appropriate interpolation of the data based on the radial basis function is performed in order to represent the dissipated energy on a continuous domain. The result of this interpolation allows us to obtain a map of the dissipated energy as a function of frequency and displacement as depicted in Figure 20(a). The darker regions on the map correspond to the highest values of the dissipated work, while the white regions are those in which the dissipated energy is practically zero. Indeed, in this last region the work done by the sloshing forces is negligible given the lack of Rayleigh-Taylor instability which lead to violent impacts of the fluid with the walls of the tank. The non-dimensional energy dissipated by the slosh dynamics \bar{W} is represented by means of the maps in Figure 20(b) (where the blue points provides the reference to the snapshots illustrated in Figure 18). The non-dimensional map assumes very little values at the very low acceleration when the fluid motion experiences Faraday waves that are not so effective in dissipating energy. After the $1g$ iso-acceleration, we see a gradual

Figure 18: Snapshots of the sloshing response at different values of acceleration and frequency for the case $\alpha = 0.50$.

Figure 19: Sloshing force and hysteresis cycle for the point 6 ($a_0 = 3g$, $f = 17Hz$) and for the fill level case $\alpha = 0.50$.

increase to a higher dissipation level in conjunction with the transition to a more chaotic regime. The second set of experiments concerns the filling level case $\alpha = 0.25$. The same set of results and analyses of the case $\alpha = 0.50$ have been obtained, where the decrease in water level considerably influences dissipation. The results in terms of dimensional and non-dimensional dissipation are shown in Figure 21. The last set of experiments concerns the case with $\alpha = 0.75$. Figure 22(a) provides the interpolated values of dissipated energy. Again, the non-dimensional dissipated work is provided in Figure 22(b) as a function of non-dimensional frequency and amplitude. As opposed to the $\alpha = 0.50$ and $\alpha = 0.25$ cases, the map of non-dimensional dissipated work tends to be more homogeneous since, on one hand there is less dissipation at higher values of acceleration since the distance that the liquid can travel inside the tank is shorter (due to the higher filling level) and the liquid particles are unable to get accelerated at a relative speed value such as to generate violent impacts, and on the other hand, at lower frequencies the fingers generated by the Faraday waves can easily reach the tank ceiling. A sensitivity analysis to the filling level is also performed on the dissipation of the fluid. Figure 23 shows the trend of dissipated energy for the three filling levels considered in the present work for the cases with $1.5g$ and $3g$ vertical acceleration, respectively, and by varying different frequencies. It can be noticed that the case $\alpha = 0.50$ filling level, is generally the more disruptive in terms of dissipated energy by varying both frequency and amplitude (except for the case of $17 Hz$).

Figure 20: Dissipated energy and non-dimensional dissipated energy distributions for the fill level case $\alpha = 0.50$.

Figure 21: Dissipated energy and non-dimensional dissipated energy distributions for the fill level case $\alpha = 0.25$.

Figure 22: Dissipated energy and non-dimensional dissipated energy distributions for the fill level case $\alpha = 0.75$.

To better understand the mechanisms that regulate energy dissipation, Figure 24 shows the isolines with 85% of the maximum of \bar{W} for three considered filling level cases, highlighting how the region in the displacement-frequency domain where most of the dissipation occurs evolves as a function of the filling level. This figure shows the location of the maximum dissipation region in the frequency-amplitude domain and its extension. Vertical sloshing always provides maximum dissipation beyond 1 g of acceleration. The filling level plays a key role as it is linked to the path that the fluid droplets must go through to impact the tank ceiling. Maximum dissipation isolines

Figure 23: Sensitivity analysis on the dissipated energy to different water filling levels.

Figure 24: Isolines with 85% of maximum of \tilde{W} for $\alpha = 0.25$, $\alpha = 0.50$ and $\alpha = 0.75$.

are all found in the region $\bar{u} = 0.2 - 0.3$ but the case $\alpha = 0.25$ seems to present higher dissipation values at higher displacement with respect to the case $\alpha = 0.75$, featured by a greater distance between the free surface and the tank ceiling. Furthermore, the greater the α , the greater the extension of the zone of maximum dissipation.

The harmonic excitation experimental analysis conducted at the University of Bristol was systematic, covering a large range of amplitudes (up to 1.6 tank heights) and frequencies (3.3 – 10.3 Hz), as shown in Figure 5. The tests were conducted at set frequencies and amplitudes of excitation, and a tank oscillation cycle averaging procedure was employed to analyse the damping force– tank displacement cycle and associated damping characteristics based upon it [6]. Since the vertical violent sloshing is chaotic in its nature, and no two sloshing cycles exhibit exactly the same characteristics, the averaging procedure ensures that persistent and underlying sloshing patterns are emphasized. Figure 25 shows the sloshing force computed according to Equation 2 as a function of tank displacement normalized to tank height A/h for the frequency of excitation $f = 8.3$ Hz and amplitude $A/h = 0.42$. Cross-cycle variance and extreme values are shown via the standard deviation curves and experimental error bars – minimum/ maximum bounds. One interesting feature of Figure 25 is that the biggest variation in F_s is seen close to the extreme values of tank displacement, near which the liquid impacts the bottom/ top of the tank and the sloshing regime is most violent. Representative snapshots characteristic of these extreme tank positions can be seen in Figures 14 & 15 in [6].

Based on the hysteresis cycles, a nondimensional energy dissipation E_c can be obtained according to Equation 3. Performing the integration across a set amplitude range and set frequency leads to a global view of the dissipation trends as shown in Figure 26, where E_c is presented as a function of the Froude number. For this series of tests, only the 8.3 Hz region in the map shown in Figure 5 was explored. Such an $E_c(Fr)$ representation is similar to what was found in the transient experiments (e.g. Figures 9 & 11). Data for the dry case is shown, as well as for the 50% water filling level case. The mean energy dissipation values as well as error bars signifying minimum/ maximum values among the analyzed tank cycles are shown. Similarly to transient experiments, different Froude numbers correspond to different liquid sloshing patterns and behaviours, R2 being found at low Fr, a transition region with occasional roof impacts at intermediate Fr, and a fully impacting R1 region at higher Fr numbers.

Figure 25: Example of sloshing hysteresis cycle used for damping analysis and sloshing variation inside the average tank cycle. Mean values, standard deviation and bounds shown.

Figure 26: Normalized energy dissipated per cycle as function of Froude number

Continuing the analogy with the UB transient experiments presented in Section 3.1, R2 and R2& R1 regions are dominated here by the same sloshing mode (2,0) as seen in Figure 8. Moving to larger amplitudes of excitation (higher Froude numbers) the system is seen to exhibit the same damping saturation behaviour where in the R1 region the non-dimensional dissipative energy E_c does not increase substantially anymore.

In order to increase the achievable excitation amplitudes and to study the behaviour of the system under different frequencies, the second actuator (long stroke electrodynamic in Figure 3) was employed at UB. Figure 27 synthesized the results that were obtained, where the Fr number parameter was replaced by the tank amplitude normalized to the tank height A/h in order to decouple the displacement amplitude from the frequency (remember that $Fr = \sqrt{A\omega^2/g}$). Figure 27 thus shows dissipation maps equivalent to those shown in Figures 20 – 22, where the interpolated experimental results are shown in the form of $E_c(A/h, f)$ isolines. It is worth noting that, as also shown in Figure 5, data at large amplitudes and frequencies at the same time is not available due to actuator limitations, the energy map being bounded by the achievable shaker accelerations. Moving from lower to larger amplitudes, for constant frequency, it can be seen that the dissipative energy increases, reaches a maximum and then it drops. This is significant since previous results obtained at UB, as shown in Figures 11 & 26 showed the damping saturation limit, without indicating the damping trends past it. Here, we see that past the maximum E_c corresponding to the damping saturation point, the dissipative energy drops and this trend is maintained regardless

Figure 27: Isolines of the dissipative energy per tank cycle for vertical harmonic excitation tests conducted at the University of Bristol. Horizontal axis: frequency; Vertical axis: amplitude

of the frequency of excitation. The existence of a maximum E_c value was also correlated in the past with a marked change in the phasing between sloshing force and tank displacement/ velocity [6, 7]. Varying the frequency of excitation (moving from left to right in Figure 27), the energy shows an increasing trend after which it reaches a plateau. The reasons for this were found to be related to the kinematics of the relative motion between the sloshing liquid and oscillating tank, as confirmed by a ballistic-harmonic numerical model in [6].

4 CONCLUSIONS

The vertical sloshing phenomenon was investigated in the context of simplified representation aircraft fuel tanks by means of a set of scaled experimental campaigns carried out by the University of Bristol (UB), La Sapienza Rome (USRS) and the Universidad Polit3cnica de Madrid (UPM). The experimental rigs were set up so that the **vertical component of the tank motion was dominant** and therefore a SDOF representation of the dynamic system was considered an accurate model. The tests were performed using two approaches:

- **transient** (step release) motion, with the initial displacement amplitude, filling level, tank size and fluid type being varied, was applied to two SDOF test rigs developed at UB(T-beam) and UPM (mass-spring system). Computation of the instantaneous damping is performed using a curvefit to the data, and the sloshing force can be achieved either directly from the experimental data or via a semi-empirical method.
- controlled **harmonic prescribed motion** of tanks with varying frequency and amplitude was applied at USRS and UB. The cyclical nature of these experiments enabled accurate computation of the energy dissipation.

In all cases, the resulting accelerations of the tank and fluid were measured along with video capture of the fluid

motion. The amplitude-frequency range of the tests between the different parties overlapped each other and covered the regions where the typical vertical sloshing regimes are representative of aircraft wing structures.

The main findings from the experiments were:

Transient Tests

- the addition of vertically sloshing fluid adds damping to a SDOF system transient motion
- the amount of added damping depends upon the filling level of the liquid, a maximum value is obtained for 50% fill level and reduces in a symmetric manner about this value i.e. 25% fill level gives roughly the same damping as 75% fill level.
- as the transient response decays, the amount of damping changes and typically follows three distinct regions depending upon the amplitude of the motion with time:
 - R1 - the most dissipative region dominated by violent vertical liquid impacts with the top and bottom of the tank
 - R2 - substantial energy dissipation caused by lower amplitude sloshing motion dominated by one of the lateral liquid sloshing modes (Faraday waves)
 - R3 - low amplitude surface ripples or no liquid movement at all and the energy dissipation is the same as the low amplitude dry structure
- the maximum R1 damping value varies with initial amplitude / maximum acceleration - initially increasing rapidly in a linear manner, up to roughly 4g, and then slowly reducing linearly with a further increase in initial amplitude / maximum acceleration
- the scaling behaviour of the damping shows the same trends when varying the filling level, initial amplitude and liquid density

Harmonic Tests

- the harmonic tests confirmed the transient test results in that the maximum dissipated energy (damping) is achieved at 50% fill level and that this is amplitude and fill level dependent.
- the energy dissipation is frequency dependent, with the maximum being found when the R1 region is excited and there is a distinct optimum excitation frequency beyond which the energy dissipation reduces
- it is possible to excite the R2 region and also a frequency range between R2 and R1 which gives a combination of both fluid motions
- above a certain acceleration (around 4 g) the dissipation mechanisms become less efficient.
- the scaling of the damping mechanism depends on the tank dimensions as well as the Froude number and filling level
- the mechanisms for the observed behaviour can be explained in terms of kinematics of the bulk motion of the liquid relative to the tank and the phase changes between the forcing and fluid response motions.

The repeatability of the test results achieved by the three independent test facilities gives a significant level of confidence in these findings, which have uncovered some of the fundamental physics of vertical sloshing motions. Interested readers are encouraged to consult the references, which give further details of the described experiments and other complementary work.

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